

Relative Effectiveness of The Use of Subject Specialist and Generalist Teaching Approaches on Academic Achievement of Pupils in Primary Schools in Anambra State, Nigeria

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<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3838924>

Abstract

The study was designed to investigate the relative effectiveness of the use of specialist and generalist teaching approaches on academic achievements of primary school pupils. The study employed equivalent not control group quasi-experimental design. The sample of study comprised 133 pupils drawn from two primary schools located at Nnamdi Azikiwe University Nursery / Primary School (NAUNPS), Awka as experimental groups A and Nnewi as experimental group B. Cluster sampling technique was used to select one arm in the school (primary four). Four intact classes, comprising of 101 pupils in school A and 32 pupils in school B were used. Four teachers in school 'A' who specialized in English Language (A), Mathematics (B), Basic Science(C) and Social Studies (D) were selected from the teachers on ground to teach the experimental group A. They rotated among the three classes of primary four to teach their specialized subjects while the experimental group B was taught by a generalist teacher. Four research questions and twelve hypotheses guided the study. The instrument for data collection was the (ATUPS). The data collected with ATUPS were analyzed using mean and ANCOVA. The results revealed that the specialist teaching approach more effective on pupils' academic achievements in English Language, Mathematics, Basic Science and Social studies than the generalist teaching approach. Based on the findings of this study the following recommendations were made among others: The advocacy of Federal Government on the use of specialist teaching for only core subjects should be extended to include social studies and possibly, other subjects. Furthermore, mechanisms should be set in motion, through the Universal Basic Education Commission (UBEC) and Teachers' Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN), to implement and as well monitor the implementation of this policy. Since NCE is the minimum qualification for teaching at the primary school level, the graduate teachers should in future be employed as specialist teachers.

Key words: *Specialized subject teacher, generalist teaching and relative effectiveness*

Introduction

Primary education is crucial to the promotion of positive development in children. It is particularly important in laying solid foundation for acquisition of knowledge and skills that will enable the child function effectively in the society. Since the rest of the educational system is

dependent on and built upon it, the primary education level is the key to the success or failure of the whole system” (Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2004:14).

Laying a solid foundation for other levels of education demands that primary education attains its objectives which include; inculcating permanent literacy, numeracy and the ability to communicate effectively; providing a sound scientific, critical and reflective thinking and promote patriotism, fairness, understanding and national unity,...(FRN, 2008,p.14). The child, the subject and the teacher are at the epicenter of educational experiences needed to meet these objectives.

The teacher is pivotal to the successful implementation of the curriculum. To ensure quality teaching and learning at the primary levels, the minimum qualification for teaching in primary schools was upgraded from Teacher’s Grade II Certificate (TCH) to Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE). Furthermore, die FRN (2008, p.21) states: “Specialist teachers shall be provided for particular subjects such as Mathematics, Basic Science & Technology, Physical & Health Education, Language Arts (in relation to English, Arabic, French, Sign Language and Nigerian Languages), Music, Fine Art and Home Economics”. Evidently, it is expected that teaching and learning of core subjects in primary schools require that every child must receive excellent instruction from professionals specifically trained and committed to teaching particularly the core subjects in primary education curriculum. This was further promoted by the provision of teacher performance standards which stipulate, among other things, that teachers should know; the content of the subjects they teach and how to teach the subjects to their students (pedagogical knowledge); the national curriculum requirements; literacy and numeracy; the diverse socio-cultural, ethnic and religious backgrounds of students and effects of these factors on learning. The professional skills they are to exhibit, include but not limited to; planning, resourcefulness, teaching and communication skills, evaluation of learners’ performance, reporting, record keeping and programme monitoring and evaluation, creating and sustaining exciting learning environment based on excellent classroom management and leadership skills (Teacher Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN), 2010,pp.1-2). Specifically, the TRCN provided that the primary school teacher (NCE holder) is expected to know all the subjects being taught in the primary school and the pedagogical skills required to teach them. In view of the expansion in primary school curriculum and the pre-service training which prepare the primary school teacher as subject specialist, the possibility of a generalist teacher meeting these performance expectations and uplifting the academic achievement of primary school pupils is doubtful.

This expectation is greater now that most primary schools in Nigeria face a myriad of challenges ranging from children with diverse needs to English language learners struggling with learning to read, and to those who have phobia for numerals (Abdul, 2008). Therefore the need to lay high academic foundation for Nigerian children particularly in the English Language, Mathematics, Basic Sciences and Social Studies have created huge demand for specialist teachers prepared to address these issues. To drive home this point, Masters (2009) asserted that ideally, every primary school teacher should be an expert teacher of literacy, numeracy and science. Like

Nigeria's National Policy on Education, he also advocated for the employment of specialist teachers.

Subject specialist is defined as one who has training in a specific discipline taken as a major in undergraduate studies or taken throughout the university education programme (Boscariol & Neden, 2008). This training prepares the teacher with the knowledge and skills necessary to bring about effective teaching of the specific subject. Stevens (2004) argued that teacher preparation can better meet teachers' needs if training will be focused on measurable outcomes and more knowledge of theory and principles that describe how instruction influences learning. He further explained that teachers are not provided with professional development needed to implement an innovative programme and that a specialist instead of a generalist teacher in mathematics has better background, will be more experienced about mathematical ideas, and will understand the relationships between concepts and units that are being studied. This will make the pupils to see the wholesomeness of mathematics and develop logical and critical thinking.

Despite the provisions of National Policy on Education for subject specialist core areas of the curriculum, generalist teaching approach which implies one teacher teaching all subjects in the primary school curriculum and stays longer time with the students in the classroom, remains the common practice in most primary schools in Nigeria. This practice belies the provisions of National Policy on Education and the TRCN's teaching standards.

A number of international scholars, particularly from the United States of America, find support for the use of generalist approach which they commonly call the "self contained" approach. Reed (2002), stimulates communication between parents and specific teacher in regard to their children's progress; and makes the teachers' solely responsible of the curriculum all day. McGrath and Rust (2002) also stated that generalist teaching allows teachers to know their pupil's strength, weaknesses, and personality traits which enable better accommodation of pupil's individual learning challenges and styles.

Similarly, a considerably large body of literature from the United States shows that the generalist teaching approach has met with some criticisms. Ardzejewska, McMaugh, and Coutts (2010) because of transfer of ineffectiveness by teachers who lack in-depth knowledge, skill and expertise in the subject they are assigned to teach. Generalist teaching compels teachers to handle subjects in which they might feel least competent. Inevitably, teachers' weaknesses in the given subjects are passed on to their pupils. The fact remains that teachers cannot teach effectively and enthusiastically what they have not mastered themselves.

Locally, a number of issues demand a re-examination of the current practice of generalist teaching approach in primary schools. These include expansion in the primary school curriculum, evidences of adequate content knowledge of teachers in relevant core areas and failure of pupils in external examinations. In the past, pivotal teachers or TCII teachers were trained and prepared

in the now abolished Teacher Training Colleges to teach all subjects. Then, the curriculum was not as crowded as it is now and the teachers were doing well as generalist teachers and the standard of education was higher. The prevalent circumstance in primary school education system is complex, in that teachers are trained to be specialist teachers but are employed and deployed to classrooms as generalist teachers.

The use of generalist teaching approach, as noted by Cannon (2011) demands that the teacher is a subject generalist who is prepared in that tradition. Despite the fact that teacher preparation now takes longer time, the quality of training expected to equip teachers adequately with the rudiments of teaching in primary schools is yet to manifest. This deficiency increases the need for specialist teaching approach as a remedial solution. Outside Nigeria, the new trend is the use of specialist teachers in primary school setting. In England, for instance, according to Alexander, Rose and Woodhead (1992), the idea of a generalist approach is outdated and does not reflect practice. They opined that due to widening subject contents, particularly in science and mathematics, it seems no longer possible for just one teacher to teach all the subjects in a class. It is assumed that only a teacher who has specialized in a discipline can effectively deliver on the subject. In Obijiofor (2011) article, he opined that mass failure in examinations conducted in Nigeria has become the most basic criterion used by the public to assess the quality of education at secondary and tertiary education levels. Primary school, being the foundation of the above mentioned level is the most critical. Again, Kwara State Ministry of Education's assessment, according to Inyang (2008), of a total of 19,125 teachers in the State's public school system among whom were 2,628 university graduates. The teachers were given tests that were designed originally for primary four pupils in English and Mathematics. As reported by the Commissioner for Education, at the end of the exercise, only seven teachers out of the 19, 125 crossed the minimum aptitude and capacity threshold. Only one out of the 2,628 graduate teachers passed the test, 10 graduates scored outright zero. The teachers fared worse in literacy assessments which recorded only 1.2% pass rate. Further to this, Adedeji's (2008) research findings showed that 77% of the sampled teachers had low level of mastery of primary mathematics while only 3.97% exhibited high competences in the content of the subject.

Adedeji (2008) reported that Primary school pupils have been performing poorly. It is therefore important to beef up pupils' achievements in basic school subjects. The result of this study may be used to determine the effect of subject specialist and generalist teaching approaches on English Language, Mathematics, Basic Science, and Social Studies which would consequently show the better approach to continue with.

In Chicago, United States, Harris (1996) conducted a research to examine whether departmentalization affected sixth grade students achievement in Reading. It was a pretest and posttest experimental design made up of random sample of 60 students which consisted of 30 students each in experimental and control groups from one school in low socio-economic area. Students' achievement was measured by Iowa Tests of Basic Skills. The data was analyzed using

t-test. The major finding was that students in the control group (self-contained) showed higher and more consistent growth in reading achievement than those in experimental group (departmentalized).

McGrath, (2008) carried out a research on the use of Mathematics specialists and mathematic coaches across the schools in United States, and effort to improve instruction and learning in mathematics, even though little research exploring their effectiveness exists. Mathematics specialists in this work refer to those who work directly with students while mathematics coaches refer to those who work directly with teachers. The purpose of the study is geared towards improving instructional practices, designing coaching programs and improving student achievements. The result showed that using Mathematics specialists at the elementary school level allowed teachers more time to effectively plan lessons and focus on their professional development, hi addition, teachers in the study reported gains in students' achievements as a result of mathematics specialists. The recommendation showed that the available empirical and anecdotal evidence suggest that coaching and mathematics specialist are professional development practices that lead to improved teaching and learning. It has been observed based on the above study that the quality of instruction by specialist teacher has a strong impact on students learning.

Two years later, the same study was extended by Yearwood (2011) in the same state by using Reading and Mathematics as dependent variables. The aim of the study was to determine whether fifth grade students taught under departmentalized classroom scored higher in Reading and Mathematical (measured by Georgia Criterion Referenced Competency Test) than students taught under the self contained classrooms in elementary schools. The study adopted a causal comparative research design. The sample of the study consisted of 1,186 fifth grade students in departmentalized classrooms in 16 schools and 966 fifth grade students in traditional. Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used to analyze the data collected. The findings of the study showed that students taught under the departmentalized (specialist teaching) scored higher on the reading and Mathematics portions of 2010 Criterion Referenced Competency Test (CRCT) than those taught under self-contained (generalist teaching). These two studies from Georgia learnt support to the use of specialist teaching.

Ardzejewski, Mcmaugh and Coutts (2010) carried out a survey on the delivery of primary curriculum in New South Wales (NSW). In Australia, the primary teacher is by and large considered a generalist; however a current paradox exists whereby there are claims that specialists are needed to deliver the curriculum. This study explores this claim by first addressing the relevance of specialist use in NSW government schools before examining principals' views regarding the current work of primary teachers. Data was collected using a mixed method sequential QUAN+QUAL design. In phase I questionnaires were distributed to all principals (N = 1608) in government primary schools in one Australian state (New South Wales) with a response rate of 25%. Follow-up interviews were conducted with 14 principals in phase II. The

findings suggest that there is a disjuncture between the assumption that the primary curriculum can be delivered by a generalist and current practices which forces us to consider whether it is time for a different model.

Shawn (2009), carried out a survey on the Impact of Departmentalization (specialist teaching) in Missouri, United States of America. The purpose of this study was to find out if there was a relationship between departmentalization and 6th grade students' achievement on the Missouri Achievement Programme (MAP). The research design used was an ex-post-facto design. Stratified random sampling was used to select the population for the study. The findings of this study indicated that best practice in middle school math was supported by reformed departmentalization where the best of teacher expertise and willingness to adopt progressive team-taught pedagogy were combined. It was observed that non-departmentalized schools have higher mean scores in the advanced and proficient range of achievement. To determine whether those differences were statistically significant, a One Sample t-test, with ninety-five percent confidence interval was performed. Studies that focus on achievement in subjects such as science and social studies could also give more information about the practice of departmentalization at the sixth grade level.

Similarly, Page (2009) conducted the same study in Missouri. However while Shawn focused on the departmentalization on science and social studies, Page was concerned with determining the effect of departmentalization (specialist teaching) and non-departmentalization (Generalist teaching approach) on sixth grade students' achievement in Communication Arts and Mathematics components of Missouri Assessment Programme (MAP). The research design was however not specified. The study sample consisted of 373 students (282 from departmentalized and 191 from non-departmentalized). Using t-test, to test the hypothesis, it was found that students taught under departmentalized classrooms (specialist teaching) and those in non-departmentalized classrooms did not differ in Mathematics and Communication Arts scores of the Missouri Assessment Programme (MAP). These two studies conducted in the same state within the same time frame came out with conflicting findings. This may be related to the sample drawn and analytic methods used by the scholars.

The purpose of the research carried out by Cannon (2011) to compare the achievement of Students in Reading and Mathematics between students that participated in the Scholastic READ 180 program within self-contained classroom instructional formats, departmentalized classrooms and students that were not enrolled in READ 180. The sample of the study consisted of 42 4th and 5th grade students of READ 180 programme from self-contained classrooms, 57 4th and 5th grade students of READ 180 programme from departmentalized classrooms and 100 4th and 5th grade students who were not enrolled in the READ 180 program. The design was a quantitative research design. Academic achievement was measured by Tennessee Comprehensive Assessment programme (TCAP). Analysis of variance was used to analyze the data. The findings indicated

no significant difference in students' Reading and Mathematics achievement taught in departmentalized and self-contained classrooms.

Ardzejewska, McMaugh, and Coutts, (2010) did a survey on the delivery of the primary curriculum. This topic has been subjected to recent debate in Western countries. In Australia, the primary teacher is by and large considered a generalist; however a current paradox exists whereby there are claims that specialists are needed to deliver the curriculum. This study explores this claim by first addressing the prevalence use of specialist in NSW government schools before examining principals' views regarding the current work of primary teachers. Data were collected using a mixed method sequential QUAN+QUAL design. In phase I questionnaires were distributed to all principals (N = 1608) in government primary schools in one Australian state (New South Wales) with a response rate of 25%. Follow-up interviews were conducted with 14 principals in phase II. The findings suggested that there is a disjuncture between the assumption that the primary curriculum can be delivered by a generalist and current practices which forces us to consider whether it is time to try a different model.

There is a dearth of research works on generalist and specialist teaching approaches in Nigeria. Njelita (2005) seems to be the only related empirical work to the study in Nigeria. He examined the primary school pupils' level of acquisition of science process skills when taught by specialist teacher and non specialist teacher. The instrument for data collection was the performance test on science process skills (PTSPS). The result reveals that; Pupils exhibited low performance in the science process skills task. There is no significant difference in the performance of boys and girls. Pupils in urban schools performed better than those in the rural schools. Pupils taught by specialist teachers performed better than those taught by non- specialist teachers. Most of the research studies revealed low performance of students in the science process skills task among students.

What was evident in these empirical studies is the contradictory findings. While some found the specialist teaching more effective, others found generalist approach more effective. Still others noted no significant difference between the two approaches. This is not surprising as contexts, grade used and measures of academic might be quite diverse and varied.

Smith (1977) propounded the theory of Division of Labour which is under management theories. Smith's main focus, the Wealth of Nations lies in the concept of economic growth. Growth, according to Smith, is rooted in the increasing division of labour. And division of labour relates primarily to the specialization of the labour force, essentially the breaking down of large jobs into many tiny components. Under this regime, each worker becomes an expert in one isolated area of production, thus increasing his efficiency. He also described division of labour as a form of specialization in which the production of a product or service is divided into several separate tasks, each performed by one person. Inherent within the specialization and division of labour is knowledge of the precise limit of each worker's "sphere of competence," and the authority to perform individual tasks without overlapping. However, Smith recognized the

potential problems of this development. He pointed out that forcing individuals to perform mundane and repetitious tasks would lead to an ignorant, dissatisfied work force. For this reason, he advanced the revolutionary belief that governments had an obligation to provide education to workers which could combat the deleterious effects of factory life as he found labour to be the source of value.

Specialization and concentration of the workers on their single subtasks often lead to greater skill and greater productivity on their particular subtasks than would be achieved by the same number of workers each carrying out the original broad task. Therefore, division of labour is assigning human resources to roles where they are most proficient in order to increase efficiency, effectiveness and productivity. The classic principles of division of labour and specialization still exist; however, their application produces both functional and dysfunctional consequences in the increasingly complex organizations. A number of factors affect the modern application of division of labour. These factors include information technology, worker empowerment, human factors, communication systems, organizational size, competitive pressures, and organizational structure.

To apply this theory to current study, the task or labour is the teaching of primary school pupils, the worker is the primary school teacher, and the various tasks are the subjects to be taught. Division of labour is assigning a teacher to teach one subject while the non-division of labour means a teacher teaching all the subjects. The consideration of teacher's subject specialization by assigning one subject to the teacher is expected to lead to further specialization and more competence in teaching of the subjects. This results in teacher effectiveness/ efficiency which is shown in content knowledge, higher pedagogical knowledge and skills and high quality lesson delivery while the teaching of numerous subjects by generalist teacher leans more towards low content knowledge, low pedagogical knowledge / skill and low quality teaching. Productivity in Adam's Smith theory means high output. However in education it means high academic achievement or increased number of successful graduates.

The implication of this theory for this study is that a teacher assigned to teach one subject to student (called specialist teacher) is more likely to have deeper / higher content knowledge, higher pedagogical knowledge of that subject and the skills required to teach that subject. With these resources, he or she will provide quality lessons to the students. This in turn will lead to increased learning and high academic achievement. However, when a teacher teaches all subjects (generalist teacher), he or she is more likely to have low content knowledge, low pedagogical knowledge/skills and low quality lesson delivery. These may more likely lead to limited learning and low academic achievement among students.

There are currently reports of poor content knowledge and lack of instructional competence among the primary school teachers. At the national level, a survey by National Teachers Institute (NTI) (2011) on the conditions of teaching of the core subjects such as (primary science, mathematics, English and social studies) indicates that primary school teachers are generally incompetent in teaching and fail to demonstrate the requisite skill for improvising and

using instructional materials. Similar report was made in Kwara State by the Commissioner for Education in 2008. An aptitude and capacity test was organized for a total of 19,125 teachers in Kwara State's Public School System, out of these, 2,628 were university graduates. The teachers were given tests that were designed originally for primary four pupils in English and Mathematics. At the end of the exercise, only seven teachers out of the 19,125 crossed the minimum aptitude and capacity threshold. Only one out of the 2,628 graduate teachers passed the test, 10 graduates scored outright zero. The teachers fared worse in literacy assessments which recorded only 1.2% pass rate.

It would seem, therefore, that these impact negatively on students' academic achievement although no mention was made about the teachers' areas of specialization. At international level, a World Bank research in which learning achievements in 22 countries in sub-Sahara and North Africa are compared, pupils in Nigeria's primary schools were the lowest with national mean scores of 30% compared with 70% in Tunisia and 51% in Mali. The situation is not different at state level.

In the face of the curricula expansion, there have been growing demands on primary school teachers and decline in pupils' academic performance. As a result, scholars in the field of education have undertaken huge research projects and it seemed greater attention were devoted to teaching methods. However, one important problem that hinges on the reluctance to implement Federal Governments' directive on the use of specialist teachers in primary schools remained unresolved. This reluctance could be attributed to uncertainty of relevant stakeholders of specialist teaching effectiveness. The problem of this study therefore, is to determine the effect of the use of subject specialist teaching approach on academic achievement of primary school pupils in the core subjects in primary schools in Anambra State when compared with those taught by generalist teachers.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to ascertain the effect of the use of subject specialist and generalist teaching approaches on pupils' academic achievement in primary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, the study;

1. examined whether primary four pupils (4th grade) taught under subject specialist approach (departmentalized classroom) scored higher in English Language than students taught under the generalist teaching approach (self contained classrooms) in primary schools.
2. examined whether primary four pupils (4th grade) taught under subject specialist approach (departmentalized classroom) scored higher in mathematics than students taught under the generalist teaching approach (self contained classrooms) in primary schools,
3. examined whether primary four pupils (4th grade) taught under subject specialist approach (departmentalized classroom) scored higher in Basic Science than students

taught under the generalist teaching approach (self contained classrooms) in primary schools

4. examined whether primary four pupils (4th grade) taught under subject specialist approach (departmentalized classroom) scored higher in Social Studies than students taught under the generalist teaching approach (self contained classrooms) in primary schools.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study;

1. What is the relative effectiveness of subject specialist teaching approach on primary school pupils' academic achievement in English Language when compared with achievement of pupils taught with generalist teaching approach using their pretest and posttest mean scores?
2. What is the relative effectiveness of subject specialist teaching approach on primary school pupils' academic achievement in Mathematics when compared with achievement of pupils taught with generalist teaching approach using their pretest and posttest mean scores?
3. What is the relative effectiveness of subject specialist teaching approach on primary school pupils' academic achievement in Basic Studies when compared with achievement of pupils taught with generalist teaching approach using their pretest and posttest mean scores?
4. What is the relative effectiveness of subject specialist teaching approach on primary school pupils' academic achievement in Social Studies when compared with achievement of pupils taught with generalist teaching approach using their pretest and posttest mean scores?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were stated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores in English Language of pupils taught with subject specialist and generalist teaching approaches.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores in Mathematics of pupils taught with subject specialist and generalist teaching approaches.
3. There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores in Basic Science of pupils taught with subject specialist and generalist teaching approaches.
4. There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores in Social studies of pupils taught with subject specialist and generalist teaching approaches.

Method

This study employed a Quasi-experimental Research Design. Akuezuilo and Agu (2015) explained that quasi experimental research design could be used in a school setting where it is not always possible to use pure experimental design which they consider as the disruption of

school activities. The specific design the researcher employed was a 2x2 pretest posttest non-equivalent control group factorial design. In this design there was both experimental groups A and B. Intact classes were used. The design adopted has enabled the researchers to examine the relative effectiveness of subject specialist and generalist teaching approaches on pupils' academic achievement.

The population of this study is 1001 primary school pupils in Nnamdi Azikiwe University Primary school pupils. This number consists of 767 pupils from Awka campus and 234 pupils from Nnewi campus. The two schools are headed by one Head teacher and controlled by one Board of Governors. The policy guidelines, mission and vision are the same. They operate the same scheme of work, write the same internal examination. Both write the same external examination with the public schools in Anambra State. They wear the same uniforms and maintain the same school programme. Most of the parents of the children are staff of the university living around Awka and Nnewi. The choice to use the schools may allow for maximum co-ordination of the experiment since the researcher is conversant with the areas as the Headmistress of the schools.

A sample of 133 pupils was used for this study. This was drawn from four intact classes of primary four, consisting of three classes of 101 pupils at Nnamdi Azikiwe University Nursery/Primary School, Awka, as experimental group A and one class of 32 pupils at Nnewi as experimental group B. Cluster sampling technique was used to randomly select one arm (primary 4). Its equivalent in Nnewi campus was used as control group.

The instrument used in this study was Achievement Test for Upper Primary School (ATUPS). It was constructed by the researchers using the Universal Basic Education Curriculum on English Language, Mathematics, Basic Science and Social Studies. The ATUPS was constructed according to the four subjects' first curriculum comprising 20 questions from each subject with four multiple choice test items. The test items were specifically used to measure the academic achievement level of the pupils in the four core subjects. The following procedure and stages were adopted in the development of the instrument (ATUPS);

- 1) Curriculum for the four subjects/item generation; the new 9-year Basic Education Curriculum Scheme of Work for Primary Four (2016) on English Language, Mathematics, Basic Science and Social Studies was used. Preliminary draft was constructed based on the various constructs that make up the test items, ensuring that all dimensions of the subjects were covered. An operation blue print/table of specification was used as a guide for the construction of the draft of 100 questions from which 80 items of academic achievement tests were selected
- 2) Organization of items: the draft instrument consisted of 80 items covering the four core subjects. The instrument was designed with hope that it would measure academic achievement. Achievement test was specifically constructed and each item has 4 multiple questions with one of them as the answer. The answers of the items carry the same weight.
- 3) Pilot testing/trial testing: after the face validation, 80-item instrument was produced and trial tested on 20 primary four pupils of a contemporary school, University Primary School, University of Nigeria, Nsukka, Enugu State.

The instruments for the four achievement tests were validated by three experts in the departments of Educational Management and Policy, Measurement and Evaluation and Guidance and Counseling, from the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University. It was also given to an expert on the field, Area Inspector of Education, Awka South, Awka Education zone. These experts were requested to assess the relevance, adequacy and comprehensiveness of the items of the tests. To guide the experts in the validation exercise, the topic of study, purpose of study, statement of problem, research questions and hypotheses, together with the draft instrument were given to the experts. These efforts were made to ensure that the instruments: English Language, Mathematics, Basic Science and Social Studies measure what they supposed to measure.

The collected 20 copies of ATUPS were administered by the researchers, to the primary four pupils of University Primary School, University of Nigeria, Nsukka. The data were used to determine the internal consistency of the instrument. Cronbach alpha procedure was used in testing the internal consistency of the items for scores derived from the trial test and it yielded a reliability coefficient of , 0.86, 0.83, 0.79, for English Language, Mathematics, Basic Science and Social Studies respectively.

Experimental Procedure

The instrument (ATUPS) was administered separately to both experimental groups, subject by subject basis in four consecutive periods and this served as pre- test. This was followed by the treatment which lasted for one term of 10 weeks. After 10 weeks, the post- test was administered to the experimental and control groups.

The four achievement tests were administered to the research subjects (pupils) in the experimental groups, before the treatment. This is called the pre - test. The test items were re-arranged and administered again to the pupils as Post - test after the treatment. Mean scores were used to analyze the research questions. A gained mean of 20.00 was considered very effective, 15.00 was regarded as effective while 10.00 regarded as fairly effective. Analysis of co-variance (ANCOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses at 0. 05 level of significance. ANCOVA was used in order to take care of the initial differences in the ability levels among the pupils.

Results

Table 1: Pretest and Posttest Mean Scores in English language for Pupils taught with subject specialist and generalist teaching approach

Source of Variation	N	Pretest X	Posttest X	Gained X	Remark
Subject Specialist Approach	101	10.40	82.44	72.04	More effective
Generalist Approach	32	10.72	67.06	56.34	

Tale 1 shows that with pretest mean score of 10.40 and posttest mean score of 82.44 with gained mean 72.04 for the pupils taught with the Subject Specialist teaching Approach as against pretest mean score of 10.72 and posttest mean score of 67.06 with gained mean of 56.34 for the pupils taught under generalist teaching Approach. Therefore, Subject Specialist teaching Approach is more effective in enhancing academic achievement of pupils in English language.

Table 2: Pretest and Posttest Mean Scores in Mathematics for Pupils taught with subject specialist and generalist teaching approaches

Source of Variation	N	Pretest X	Posttest X	Gained X	Remark
Subject Specialist Approach	101	6.30	56.41	50.11	More effective
Generalist Approach	32	11.84	55.00	43.16	

Table 2 indicates that with pretest mean score of 6.30 and posttest mean score of 56.41 with gained mean 50.11 for the pupils taught with the Subject Specialist teaching Approach as against pretest mean score of 11.84 and posttest mean score of 55.00 with gained mean of 43.16 for the pupils taught under generalist teaching Approach. Therefore, Subject Specialist teaching Approach is more effective in enhancing academic achievement of pupils in Mathematics.

Table 3: Pretest and Posttest Mean Scores in Basic Science for Pupils taught with subject specialist and generalist teaching approaches

Source of Variation	N	Pretest X	Posttest X	Gained X	Remark
Subject Specialist Approach	101	8.60	66.28	57.68	More effective
Generalist Approach	32	9.56	51.09	41.53	

Table 3 reveals that with pretest mean score of 8.60 and posttest mean Score of 66.28 with gained mean 57.68 for the pupils taught with the Subject Specialist teaching Approach as against pretest mean score of 9.56 and posttest mean score of 51.09 with gained mean of 41.53 for the pupils taught under generalist teaching Approach. Therefore, Subject Specialist teaching Approach is more effective in enhancing academic achievement of pupils in Basic Science.

Table 4: Pretest and Posttest Mean Scores in Social studies for Pupils taught with subject

Source of Variation	N	Pretest X	Posttest X	Gained X	Remark
Subject Specialist Approach	101	8.09	68.63	60.54	More effective
Generalist Approach	32	10.72	58.94	48.22	

Table 4 shows that with pretest mean score of 8.09 and posttest mean score of 68.63 with gained mean 60.54 for the pupils taught under the Subject Specialist teaching Approach as against pretest mean score of 10.72 and posttest mean score of 58.94 with gained mean of 48.22 for the pupils taught under generalist teaching Approach. Therefore, Subject Specialist teaching Approach is more effective in enhancing academic achievement of pupils in Social studies.

Table 5: ANCOVA on the Mean achievement Scores in English language for Pupils taught with subject specialist and generalist teaching approaches

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	Cal.F	Crit.F	p≥0.05
Corrected Model	5785.706	2	2892.853			
Intercept	43527.466	1	43527.466			
English I	42.623	1	42.623			
Methods	5778.278	1	5778.278	20.96	3.84	S
Error	35836.084	130	275.662			
Total	866154.000	133				
Corrected Total	41621.789	132				

In table 5, it was observed that at 0.05 level of significance, ldf numerator and 132df denominator, the calculated F 20.96 is greater than the critical F 3.84. The first null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is significant difference in the mean achievement scores in English language of pupils taught with subject specialist teaching approach when compared with mean achievement scores of those taught with generalist teaching approach.

Table 6: ANCOVA on the Mean achievement Scores in Mathematics for Pupils taught with subject specialist and generalist teaching approaches

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	Cal.F	Crit.F	p≥0.05
Corrected Model	2898.286	2	1449.143			
Intercept	8485.694	1	8485.694			
Maths I	2850.251	1	2850.251			
Methods	1984.756	1	1984.756	7.138	3.84	S
Error	36148.105	130	278.062			
Total	457143.000	133				
Corrected Total	39046.391	132				

Table 6 shows that at 0.05 level of significance, ldf numerator and 132df denominator, the calculated F 7.14 is greater than the critical F 3.84. The second null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is significant difference in the mean achievement scores in mathematics of pupils taught with subject specialist teaching approach when compared with mean achievement scores of those taught with generalist teaching approach.

Table 7: ANCOVA on the Mean achievement Scores in Basic science for Pupils taught with subject specialist and generalist teaching approaches

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	Cal.F	Crit.F	p≥0.05
Corrected Model	5955.732	2	2977.866			
Intercept	44004.956	1	44004.956			
Basicsciencel	353.486	1	353.486			

Methods	58397.992	1	5865.992	14.02	3.84	S
Error	54397.471	130	418.442			
Total	581949.000	133				
Corrected Total	60353.203	132				

Table 7 shows that at 0.05 level of significance, ldf numerator and 132df denominator, the calculated F 14.02 is greater than the critical F 3,84. The third null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is significant difference in the mean achievement scores in Basic science of pupils taught with subject specialist teaching approach when compared with mean achievement scores of those taught with generalist teaching approach.

Table 8: ANCOVA on the Mean achievement Scores in Social, studies for Pupils taught with subject specialist and generalist teaching approaches

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	Cal.F	Crit.F	p≥0.05
Corrected Model	3368.445	2	1684.223			
Intercept	26870.286	1	26870.286			
Social Studies I	1083.796	1	1083.796			
Methods	3237.327	1	3237.327	7.19	3.84	S
Error	58547.525	130	450.366			
Total	646556.000	133				
Corrected Total	61915.970	132				

Table 8 reveals that at 0.05 level of significance, ldf numerator and 132df denominator, the calculated F 7.19 is greater than the critical F 3.84. The fourth null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is significant difference in the mean achievement scores in Social Studies of pupils taught with subject specialist teaching approach when compared with mean achievement scores of those taught with generalist teaching approaches.

Discussion of Results

Effect of subject specialist and Generalist teaching approach on pupils' academic achievement

The results of this study strongly indicate that specialist teaching approach have more positive effects on pupils' academic achievement than the generalist approach. The result of this study revealed that subject specialist teaching approach is more effective in enhancing the academic achievement in English Language than the generalist approach as shown by the 15.65 points ahead of generalist group. This result is similar to previous result obtained by Yearword (2011) in Georgia (United States) whose research showed that pupils' achievements in Reading was higher in a classroom in which a form of specialist teaching (departmentalized) was used than those taught in a one-teacher-teaches-all- subjects setting. This highly positive effect on pupils' academic achievement may be associated with the deep knowledge the specialist teacher brings to bear in the teaching of the subject. As observed by Uche (2001) teacher's mastery of English Language is the most important factor in students' performance in the subject.

However, current finding is incongruent with some previous results that suggest that generalist teaching was more effective than specialist teaching (Harris 1996; McGrath & Rust; 2002). The current result equally contrasts with others research findings that recorded no difference in academic achievement in English Language/Communication Arts between students taught using the two approaches (Cannon, 2011; Page, 2009;). Possible explanation for this incongruence lies in the teacher characteristics as some scholars have argued that the effects of specialization may largely depend on whether the high-performing or low-performing teachers specialize. Moreover, most of these studies used students from different grade levels in their studies.

The result of this study showed that subject specialist teaching approach is more effective in enhancing the academic achievement in Mathematics when compared with generalist approach as indicated by the mean gain of 8.05 in favour of specialist teaching group. This result is in consonance with results of previous studies (Delise, 2006; Yearwood, 2011). This finding lends credence to argument that it is unrealistic for a generalist teacher to have specialized knowledge to facilitate Mathematics instruction as would a mathematics specialist teacher. However, this current finding was found to be inconsistent with findings recorded by some researchers whose result noted that teacher specialization had no effect on students' achievement in Mathematics and results that indicated no significant difference in pupils achievement in Mathematics with respect to specialist teaching and generalist teaching approaches (Cannon, 2011; McGrath & Rust, 2002; Page, 2009). There appears to be more empirical evidence supporting the positive effect of specialist teaching on Mathematics achievement than the generalist approach. This seems to confirm the argument that Mathematics specialists at the elementary school level allow teachers more time to effectively plan and deliver their lessons and focus on their professional development.

The result of this study revealed that subject specialist teaching approach had greater effect on pupils' academic achievement in basic science than the generalist approach. This is shown by the difference in mean gain score (Difference in Mean gain score = 16.65) of specialist and generalist teaching groups. The finding reinforces previous empirical evidence provided Cannon (2011) who found that teacher specialization is associated with increase in upper elementary pupils' achievement in science. It is also consistent with the research findings that suggest that teacher's mastery of the subject improved interest, attention and learning attitude among pupils (Odor & Igwe, 2010). On the other hand, this current result contrasts with findings documented by some researchers which showed that teacher specialization had no effect on students' achievement in Basic Science (McGrath & Rust, 2002) and results that showed no significant difference in pupils achievement in Basic Science for two approaches.

Conclusions

The aim of this study is to examine the effect of specialist and generalist teaching approaches on primary school pupils' academic achievement. From the evidence provided from the data analysis, the researcher concludes as follows:

The specialist teaching approach is effective on pupils' academic achievements in English Language, Mathematics, Basic Science and Social studies than the generalist teaching approach.

Implications of the Study

The findings of this study have practical implications for educational administration, teaching and learning in elementary schools.

1. The findings call for a teacher assignment practices that are based on teachers' area of specialization and disciplinary domain. The head-teacher's assignment of teachers to teach each subject should be based on teacher specialization and mastery of that subject.
2. This study also has implication for teacher development. It demands teacher continuous professional development (CPD) that is more subject focused approach and directed at each teacher's area of specialization. In such a practice, enhancement of teachers' professional knowledge and skills are focused on teaching methods, strategies, techniques and instructional materials that is more appropriate to the specific subject he or she teaches.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study the following recommendations are put forward:

1. The Provision of Federal Government on the use of specialist teaching for only four core subjects should be extended to included social studies and, possibly, other subjects. Furthermore, mechanisms should be set in motion, through the Universal Basic Education Commission, to implement and as well as monitor the implementation of this policy.
2. Since NCE is the minimum qualification for teaching at the primary school level, Teachers' Professional Standard produced by the Teachers' Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN) should be modified to provide for specific content knowledge for NCE teachers and not the generalist status which they are currently accorded in the professional standards.
3. Continuing Professional Development of Primary School Teachers should mostly be tailored to suit the teachers' subject area, pedagogical skills related to the subject as well as the assessment and evaluation methods.

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